

PIRO-2025-03177

Details

Working Title Reinitiation of the PIFSC Coral Collection Activities in American Samoa

Request Received Dec 4, 2025

Region PIRO

Division Protected Resources Division (PRD)

Branch Intergovernmental Coordination and Conservation Branch

Activity Details

Category	Sub-Category
Survey	Fisheries

Primary Action Agency

US Department of Commerce (DOC) - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) - Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center

Species Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora retusa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Isopora crateriformis</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Dolphin	False Killer Whale	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>	Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	Endangered Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Indo-West Pacific DPS	Threatened Indo-West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Fish	Oceanic Whitetip Shark	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Giant Manta Ray	<i>Manta birostris</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Pinniped	Hawaiian Monk Seal	<i>Neomonachus schauinslandi</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	All Other Areas	Threatened All Other Areas	✗	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	South Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered South Pacific Ocean DPS	✗	✓
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	North Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered North Pacific Ocean DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central West Pacific DPS	Endangered Central West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central South Pacific DPS	Endangered Central South Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central North Pacific DPS	Threatened Central North Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Whale	Sei Whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	North Pacific Right Whale	<i>Eubalaena japonica</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Western North Pacific DPS	Endangered Western North Pacific DPS	✓	✗
Whale	Fin Whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Blue Whale	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Sperm Whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗

Critical Habitat Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Dolphin	False Killer Whale	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>	Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	Designated Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS
Pinniped	Hawaiian Monk Seal	<i>Neomonachus schauinslandi</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide

Location Information

Country/International Waters	Foreign Waters Jurisdictional Zone	US Waters Jurisdictional Zone	State/Territory	Body of Water	HUC Level #	HUC Number
United States		Federal Waters		North Pacific Ocean		

GIS Information

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
No GIS details available									